

INTERNATIONAL YEAR OF
Quantum Science
and Technology

QUANTUM CROSSROADS:

A vision for art, culture and quantum
science and technology

KI TE WHAI AO, KI TE AO MARAMA

Māori whakataukī/proverb

This fragment of a longer incantation recalls the process of creation moving from Te Kore, or void/potentiality, through darkness, or Te Pō, to the first glimmers of light - Te Whai Ao, and eventually to the light of day - Te Ao Mārama. It is often used as a metaphor for the stages a person passes through to reach enlightenment.

The artwork in this document was created by Jessica Hinerangi Thompson-Carr (Ngāpuhi, Ngāruahine, Ngāti Ruanui), an illustrator and poet based in Ōtepoti Dunedin, on Kāi Tahu land. She writes:

The main double spiral pattern, called a takarangi, represents creation, balance, and the expanding and vibrant nature of quantum science, technology, and arts. In the spiral are hikuaua lines to show the back-and-forth cycles we encounter, the different rhythms we see in science and our universe.

The smaller spirals, the tōrino, feature hawahawa notches, symbols or tohu of the breath or vitality of both science and art. Under these are haehae, or protection lines, set at a crossroads with each other.

Lastly, the incomplete spirals are haehae in the form of koru, with the hawahawa notches inside. The koru is a spiral inspired by the unfurling of new fern fronds, representing creation and new beginnings/life.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Quantum science and technology (QST) is entering a pivotal period in its development; significant advances in theory and application are diffusing more rapidly into everyday life, with technical and social impacts that require a radical reimagining of how we understand the world. Art and culture offer unique and critical pathways to authentically engage diverse communities with these changes, expanding imagination and social understanding to ensure quantum futures across the world are inclusive, responsible, and meaningful.¹

Thus the International Year of QST sponsored the global Quantum Crossroads event (QXroads) to gather practitioners and leaders from around the world across art, culture, education, community, Indigenous knowledge systems, and QST to craft a 10 year vision to facilitate these disciplines working together to achieve the ideal quantum future for all.

This vision treats arts, culture, and quantum science & technology as co-equal knowledge-making partners, and proposes structures where leadership, funding, and evaluation are shared across these communities.

The resulting document outlines principles, identifies key themes, and proposes programmes to inform a culturally-grounded, globally interconnected future for QST.

¹H. Andrews and A. Hawcroft (eds.), *Why technology needs artists: 40 international perspectives* (British Council, 2025). <https://doi.org/10.57884/Z34F-0732>

The waharoa, or formal gateway, at Kāti Huirapa ki Puketeraki Marae, Dunedin, NZ, where the inaugural Quantum Crossroads event began. Photo credit: Omar Costa Hamido.

1. CONTEXT AND PURPOSE

Advances in quantum technologies – such as in computing, sensing, communications, and materials science – are poised to reshape and influence multiple dimensions of society. Yet quantum literacy is often framed as a technical challenge rather than a cultural one, unnecessarily constricting public understanding of, and interaction with, QST; narratives are fragmented and lack cultural relevance and access to knowledge is unevenly distributed. These are systemic barriers and require institutional change as well as new narratives. As a result, QXroads participants reflected that, in many societal contexts, QST often evokes feelings of fear and intimidation or is associated with mystification and exceptionalism.

At the same time, however, the QXroads participants represented diverse cultural and artistic practices that have long embraced and explored concepts that QST articulates: relationality, uncertainty, entanglement, and multiplicity. From these extensive and diverse experiences, participants concluded that when quantum science is embedded in cultural or artistic practice, it becomes less distant and intimidating and becomes something in which all people can actively participate or engage with through curiosity and wonder. The goal is not persuasion, but enabling informed participation, contestation, and collective shaping of quantum futures.

In particular, participants emphasized that:

- Indigenous epistemologies, particularly those grounded in relational ontologies, are autonomous knowledge traditions with concepts that can resonate with, and challenge, quantum relationality.²
- Art and culture inspire conceptual innovation by offering alternative ways of thinking and creating new pathways for understanding complexity.
- Public narratives shape legitimacy, consent, and governance, influencing trust, ethical considerations and technological futures.

This document thus reframes quantum science as a cultural project.

²Justin Hanning, *Te Hihiri o Te Ao: Illuminating the Intersections of Mātauranga Māori and Quantum Photonics* (unpublished, 2025). See Appendix A for the full document.

Still from Quantum Voyages, a theatre piece created by Smitha Vishveshwara (Physics), Latrelle Bright (Theatre), and Stephen Taylor (Music), performed for IQ at the American Physical Society's Global Physics Summit. Photo Credit: James Gross

2. GUIDING PRINCIPLES

The guiding principles of this vision document were derived from the QXroads participants and align with UNESCO's mandate to advance education, culture, knowledge equity, and international cooperation.

- **Cultural Inclusivity**

Initiatives should be accessible across worldviews, including supporting the development of terminology in minority and Indigenous languages. Language choices will be reviewed with cultural and community advisors to avoid deficit framing and unintended pejorative readings.

- **Reciprocity & Relationality**

Initiatives should be grounded in humility, care, and respect for the cultural contexts in which knowledge is being shared.

- **Interdisciplinarity and Experimentation**

Artistic, scientific, and Indigenous methodologies all contribute to discovery and meaning-making; collaboration between these should be structurally supported in the development of the initiative. This includes shared governance, shared credit (co-authorship/curation), and dedicated cross-sector funding lines.

- **Accessibility & Open Knowledge**

Initiatives for the public should prioritize embodied, participatory approaches that lower barriers to access and understanding.

- **Long-term Capacity Building**

Initiatives should support sustainable networks, educational pathways, and institutional infrastructures.

Planetarium visitors enjoy an immersive screening of the quantum-inspired short film "Boundary of Time", a finalist in CQT's Quantum Shorts competition. Photo Credit: Jessica Barder

3. KEY THEMES FOR TRANSFORMATIVE IMPACT

These themes describe three collaboration modes that often overlap within the same project (rather than separate domains): co-research, co-creation, and public co-governance. In all three modes, initiatives should explicitly address practical conditions: differences in timelines, incentives, pay/credit norms, IP expectations, ethics review, and institutional power.

- Co-research (Arts/Culture/QST) – where artistic and cultural perspectives are integrated into research practice through co-design, shared authorship, and mutual learning to:
 - open new questions and methods across QST and artistic/cultural practice by challenging them to consider new perspectives and new modes of engagement with their theories³
 - enable shared ethical deliberation and futures practice with affected communities, futures thinking, and conceptual reflection⁴
- Co-creation (Arts/Culture/QST) – where artistic and cultural practitioners explore quantum theory/technologies alongside QST partners to:
 - provide new conceptual inspiration for innovation in work through non-QST mediums
 - expand the tools and perspectives with which to create new and innovative work through access to quantum theories and technologies⁵
- Co-governance with publics (Arts/Culture/QST) – power over agenda-setting, evaluation, resourcing, and engagement are shared, as scientists engage with art and artists engage with science to support diverse publics to:
 - shape priorities and strengthen accountability through shared decision-making and participation in how QST is developed and governed.
 - imagine and engage with shaping hopeful quantum futures that are inclusive and culturally relevant
 - recognize and exercise their existing capacity to interpret, question, and contribute to quantum debates and decisions
 - discover wholly new perspectives and vistas at this confluence through deep listening and creative synergies

³Angus Macfarlane and Sonja Macfarlane, "Listen to culture: Māori scholars' plea to researchers," *Journal of the Royal Society of New Zealand* 49 (2019): 1-10, doi:10.1080/03036758.2019.1661855.

⁴Andrews & Hawcroft, *Why technology needs artists*.

⁵Erika Brockmeier, "To celebrate quantum science's centennial, scientists embrace art and play," *American Physical Society*, April 11, 2025, <https://www.aps.org/apsnews/2025/04/quantum-science-centennial-art-play>.

Still from *Disklavier Prelude #4*, in *The Gedanken Room* (2021), a film by Omar Costa Hamido, with cinematography by Grant Speich. Photo credit: Omar Costa Hamido.

4. PROPOSED PROGRAMMES AND INITIATIVES

- Digital Infrastructure and Network – in order to grow a self-sustaining, interconnected global community of practitioners, the networks and databases already existing (Community⁶, the Science Gallery network⁷, Ars Electronica⁸, and the National Organisation of Media Arts Database⁹) are connected and expanded to host:
 - directories of available collaborators and venues
 - course materials and toolkits for new entrants to this transdisciplinary field
 - case studies, project archives, & discussion papers, such as offered in the Appendix, that capture the diversity of perspectives and methodologies that exist across the globe
 - a shared global calendar of opportunities and activities in this field
- Language Development Initiative – to advance literacy across disciplines, expand access and engagement to all, embed culturally grounded metaphors in community engagement activities and empower communities to engage with quantum ideas through their own epistemologies, a sustained effort is launched to develop quantum vocabulary in Indigenous and minority languages via paid co-translation workshops and document it in a public, community-governed glossary hosted with local institutions as stewards
- Global Summer School and Curriculum Pathways – building on existing pathways^{10,11}, transdisciplinary summer schools are run internationally to introduce students to co-taught Indigenous knowledge systems, quantum physics fundamentals, and creative methodologies¹², before undertaking exploration of ethical, cultural, and societal implications of QST through different practices. Over time, such programmes go on to integrate into secondary and tertiary taught curricula.
- Corporate and Professional Quantum Arts & Culture Programmes – mirroring existing models that have been created for AI, corporations like IBM, Google, Microsoft, and Ethereum integrate a “Quantum Arts and Culture” programme into their quantum computing divisions, while professional societies like IEEE, SPIE, and APS introduce “Quantum Arts and Culture” as a special interest area at relevant conferences
- UNESCO “City of Quantum” Designation – the creation of such a designation, embedded in the UNESCO Creative Cities Network, provides financial and/or administrative support to cities committed to integrating arts, culture, and QST through activities such as:
 - International “Entangled City” partnerships mirroring the “Sister City” community-led initiatives to foster cross-cultural collaboration on a global scale
 - Science or art residencies/fellowships designed to facilitate reciprocal learning through co-teaching cross-disciplinary courses at the tertiary level as well as encourage blue-sky exploration of ideas, resulting in a collaborative creative output.
 - Quantum-themed festivals, public art installations, performance-based workshops and productions, community and research co-creation projects, and interactive exhibitions, all that integrate arts, culture, and QST
 - Biennial Quantum Crossroads workshops hosted in a different City of Quantum each time, representing multiple knowledge systems and themes as well as coordinating an associated public-facing event such as an exhibition, competition, or hackathon, in order to continue growth and development of a global network of practitioners.
 - UNESCO declares an upcoming International Year of Art, Culture and Quantum Science and Technology – as a follow-up to 2025 and to promote further innovation for transformative impact.

⁶Community., accessed at <https://community.quantumland.art/>

⁷The Science Gallery Network, accessed at <https://sciencegallery.org/>

⁸Ars Electronica, accessed at <https://ars.electronica.art/archive/en/>

⁹National Organisation of Media Arts Database, accessed at <https://www.nomad.net.au/resources>

¹⁰Paul Thomas; “The Transdisciplinary Cloud Curriculum,” *Leonardo* 48:5 (2015): 474–475. doi: https://doi.org/10.1162/LEON_a_01070

¹¹“Flowing from Quantum to Cosmic”, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, <https://publish.illinois.edu/flowing-from-quantum-to-cosmic/>

¹²See glossary for a list of terms used in such frameworks.

IMPLEMENTATION ROADMAP

Short-Term (2026-2028)

- Pilot quantum-art summer school
- Begin artist-scientist residencies
- Create a virtual exhibition space
- Establish a UNESCO working group for the City of Quantum framework with balanced representation (arts/culture leaders, Indigenous/community representatives, educators, policymakers, and QST researchers).
- Begin process of identifying future Year of Arts, Culture, and QST
- Support minority language vocabulary development
- Increase global visibility of existing digital networks through coordinated communication channels

Medium-Term (2029-2031)

- First cohort of City of Quantum designations
- Biennial Quantum Crossroads launched
- Expanded residency network across continents
- Integration of curriculum pathways in universities and cultural institutions
- Development of evaluation metrics for impact assessment

Long-Term (2032-2035)

- Mature international network connecting cities, institutions, and communities
- Quantum Arts and Culture programmes embedded in corporate quantum research divisions and professional societies
- Sustainable global infrastructure for collaboration and public engagement
- Recognition of quantum culture as a central component of global knowledge societies

CONCLUSION

Quantum science and technology may reshape global societies, raising questions of power, responsibility, and benefit. Arts, culture, and Indigenous knowledge systems are partners in shaping how quantum futures are imagined, debated, and governed—through shared decision-making, careful attention to provenance, reciprocal benefit, and shared ethical deliberation.

By adopting this vision and implementing the proposed 10-year roadmap, UNESCO and international partners can help establish a global ecosystem where quantum science is not isolated in laboratories but woven into the cultural fabric of communities worldwide. Through coordinated programs, inclusive education, and cross-disciplinary partnerships, we can ensure that quantum technologies emerge within a framework of care, reciprocity, creativity, and global solidarity. Quantum Crossroads demonstrates that such a future is both possible and already beginning. What is needed now is collective commitment and international cooperation to carry this vision forward.

PARTICIPANTS

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GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Civic Practice: Artistic engagement focused on societal structures, policy, and community systems.
Social Practice: Art that prioritizes relationships, community collaboration, and collective creativity.
Studio Practice: Artist-centered creative work that may draw conceptual inspiration from quantum principles.
Quantum-Aided Composition (QAC): Creative processes that involve quantum computation as an exploratory tool.
Quantum Sister Cities: Paired cities collaborating on quantum-art initiatives and knowledge exchange.
Quantum Literacy: Public understanding of quantum ideas through culturally relevant frameworks.

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Appendix A: Te Hihiri o Te Ao: Illuminating the Intersections of Mātauranga Māori and Quantum Photonics

This thesis explores the profound intersections between Mātauranga Māori and quantum photonics, drawing on the work of the Dodd-Walls Centre for Photonic and Quantum Technologies (Te Whai Ao), hosted at the University of Otago. Established in January 2015 as one of New Zealand’s Centres of Research Excellence, the Dodd-Walls Centre (DWC) builds on the legacies of pioneering physicists Jack Dodd and Dan Walls. With a focus on quantum optics, photonics, ultra-cold atoms, and quantum technologies, the Centre bridges foundational physics and practical applications across agritech, medical technology, and civil engineering. This thesis proposes a kaupapa Māori epistemological and ontological framework to engage with DWC’s research, fostering a relational science that honors indigenous worldviews while advancing scientific innovation.

PURPOSE AND SCOPE

The Dodd-Walls Centre unites approximately 200 researchers and students from six New Zealand universities—Otago, Auckland, Victoria, AUT, Massey, and Canterbury—alongside international collaborators. Its evolution from the merger of the Jack Dodd Centre (Otago) and Dan Walls Centre (Auckland), coupled with a significant NZD 36.7 million funding extension in 2020 to support operations through 2028, underscores its national and global significance. The Centre pursues two flagship programs: Beacons and Quantum Technologies Aotearoa, targeting advanced computation, imaging, sensing, and communication. This thesis aligns these efforts with Māori cosmological principles—Te Kore, Te Pō, and Te Ao Mārama—to reimagine quantum research as a relational and ethical practice.

TE ARA O TE AO:

A Kaupapa Māori Epistemological Ontology for Quantum Inquiry

1. Ko Te Kore - The Primordial Void of Potential

In Māori cosmology, Te Kore represents the formless realm of infinite possibility, paralleling quantum superposition where particles exist in multiple states until observed. This resonance with the scientific unknown—Te Kē, Te Kō, Te Kōko—suggests a shared understanding of potentiality as a generative space, engaged through wānanga (deep learning).

2. Ko Te Pō - Gestation, Darkness, Entanglement

Te Pō, the realm of becoming, mirrors quantum entanglement and coherence phenomena studied at DWC. Entanglement, akin to whakapapa (interconnected relationships), implies that once connected, entities remain relationally bound. This raises ethical considerations of relationality and kaitiaki (guardianship) responsibilities toward fundamental matter.

3. Ko Te Ao Mārama - The World of Light and Form

Te Ao Mārama, the realm of light and consciousness, aligns with DWC's development of quantum sensors and photonic devices. This stage transforms unseen potential into visible innovation, yet Māori philosophy insists on cycling back to Te Kore and Te Pō through wānanga, karakia (incantations), and whakapapa-based thinking, ensuring a holistic approach.

4. Mauri, Mana, and the Intelligence of Matter

Mauri, the life force sustaining coherence, and mana, the authority to act, find parallels in quantum systems' integrity and transformative potential. Drawing on Atua frameworks—e.g., Tāwhaki's wave-particle duality and Hineraumati-Hinetakurua's photonic cycles—this thesis posits that matter possesses inherent intelligence, responsive to relational engagement.

5. Whakapapa, Entanglement, and the Ethics of Relationality

Whakapapa, the interconnected web of all things, mirrors quantum entanglement's non-local connections. This raises questions of kaitiaki responsibilities, whanaungatanga (relationships) with non-human entities, and the potential for kaupapa Māori-guided quantum technologies to enhance oranga o te taiao (environmental well-being) and oranga o te whānau (family health).

6. The Wānanga as a Methodological Model

Inspired by kaupapa Māori methodologies, this thesis proposes a wānanga model mapping quantum research phases—potentiality (superposition/Te Kore), incubation (coherence/Te Pō), manifestation (application/Te Ao Mārama), and return (reflection/ritual)—to foster a dual knowledge system.

THE DODD-WALLS CENTRE IN CONTEXT

The DWC's scientific leadership positions New Zealand as a global player in quantum and photonics research, training approximately 130 postgraduates with cutting-edge skills and bridging theory to applications in health, agriculture, technology, and security. Its outreach, including participation in the 2025 International Year of Quantum, highlights its commitment to public engagement. This thesis envisions extending this impact by integrating Māori-led research

grounded in whānau, whenua (land), and wairua (spirit), potentially drawing on Ngāi Tahu pūrākau (narratives) like Tāwhaki's ascent as a quantum exploration metaphor.

The Dodd-Walls Centre, as a beacon of scientific advancement, offers a unique opportunity to co-create a luminous world that stirs the human spirit, debates the universe, and converses with the souls of the stars. By integrating Māori ontologies of care, interconnection, and sacredness, this thesis and proposed wānanga envision a future where quantum photonics and mātauranga Māori illuminate each other, fostering a relational science that honors Aotearoa's dual heritage. With MBIE funding, this partnership can transform research, education, and innovation, ensuring a legacy of light beyond the veil.

The integration of Māori cosmology into practical applications, particularly in the context of quantum photonics and the research conducted by the Dodd-Walls Centre for Photonic and Quantum Technologies (Te Whai Ao), offers a rich framework for innovation that bridges indigenous knowledge with cutting-edge science. Based on the analysis of the provided document, Te Hihiri o Te Ao: Illuminating the Intersections of Mātauranga Māori and Quantum Photonics, the following explores potential Māori cosmology applications, focusing on how concepts such as Te Kore, Te Pō, Te Ao Mārama, mauri, mana, and whakapapa can be applied to advance research, technology, and societal outcomes.

1. Te Kore - Harnessing Infinite Potential

- **Application in Quantum Research:** Te Kore, the primordial void of potential, aligns with quantum superposition, where particles exist in multiple states until observed. This concept can inspire new approaches to quantum computing and sensing by treating the "void" as a space of untapped possibilities. Researchers could develop algorithms or experimental designs that mimic Te Kore's generative nature, exploring how uncertainty and potentiality can be leveraged to enhance computational efficiency or sensor sensitivity.
- **Practical Example:** Designing quantum systems that simulate Te Kore's infinite potential could lead to breakthroughs in quantum machine learning, where models are trained to operate in a state of probabilistic readiness, mirroring Māori wānanga (deep learning) methods of engaging with the unknown.
- **Societal Impact:** This approach could empower Māori communities to lead in quantum innovation, fostering technologies that reflect their cosmological understanding of potential as a creative force.

2. Te Pō - Relational Technologies and Entanglement

- **Application in Photonics:** Te Pō, the realm of gestation and becoming, resonates with quantum entanglement and coherence phenomena studied at the Dodd-Walls Centre. Applying this concept could guide the development of photonic devices that prioritize relational connectivity, such as entangled photon networks for secure communication or imaging systems that detect subtle interdependencies in biological or environmental systems.
- **Practical Example:** Creating entanglement-based communication protocols inspired by Te Pō emphasis on whakapapa (interconnected relationships) could enhance cybersecurity, ensuring data integrity through non-local connections. Night labs, as proposed in the wānanga, could test these systems under conditions mimicking Te Pō darkness.
- **Societal Impact:** This could support kaitiaki (guardianship) roles, enabling Māori-led monitoring of environmental health (e.g., water quality or biodiversity) using entangled sensing technologies that reflect relational ethics.

3. Te Ao Mārama - Visible Innovation and Responsibility

- **Application in Quantum Sensing:** Te Ao Mārama, the world of light and form, aligns with the Dodd-Walls Centre's work on quantum sensors and imaging. Māori cosmology's cyclical view—where light returns to Te Kore and Te Pō through wānanga and karakia—can inform the design of sustainable technologies that balance visibility with ethical stewardship.

- **Practical Example:** Developing quantum imaging tools for medical diagnostics or agricultural monitoring (e.g., crop health) could incorporate maramataka (lunar calendar) cycles to optimize data collection, ensuring alignment with natural rhythms. The wānanga hands-on labs could prototype these devices.

- **Societal Impact:** This application supports oranga o te whānau (family health) and oranga o te taiao (environmental well-being), providing Māori communities with tools to address health disparities and land management challenges.

4. Mauri and Mana - Intelligent Matter and Transformative Technologies

- **Application in Material Science:** Mauri, the life force sustaining coherence, and mana, the authority to act, suggest that matter possesses intelligence and agency. This could inspire research into quantum materials with enhanced coherence (mauri) and adaptive properties (mana), such as ultra-cold atom systems or photonic crystals.

- **Practical Example:** Engineering quantum materials that respond to environmental cues—e.g., self-regulating sensors for climate monitoring—could draw on Atua narratives like Tāwhaki (wave-particle duality) or Hinerraumati-Hinetakuruā (photonic cycles). Lab experiments during the wānanga could explore these properties.

- **Societal Impact:** Such innovations could revolutionize renewable energy or infrastructure, aligning with Māori values of reciprocity and empowering iwi-led sustainability projects.

5. Whakapapa - Ethical Frameworks for Quantum Systems

- **Application in Quantum Ethics and AI:** Whakapapa, the interconnected web of relationships, mirrors quantum entanglement and offers an ethical lens for developing quantum technologies and artificial intelligence. This could involve designing systems that acknowledge relational histories and responsibilities, guided by tikanga (customs).

- **Practical Example:** Quantum computing algorithms could incorporate whakapapa principles to ensure equitable data representation, avoiding biases that disconnect communities. The wānanga's group discussions could refine these ethical guidelines, integrating kaitiaki responsibilities.

- **Societal Impact:** This approach could foster Māori-led AI development, supporting cultural preservation and economic growth while addressing global ethical challenges in technology deployment.

6. Wānanga as a Methodological Innovation

- **Application in Research Methodology:** The wānanga model—cycling through potentiality, incubation, manifestation, and return—can serve as a methodology for collaborative research. This iterative process, blending karakia, lab work, and reflection, could structure DWC projects to integrate Māori and scientific perspectives.

- **Practical Example:** A wānanga could pilot this method, combining quantum experiments with night-sky rituals to explore light as whakapapa. Outputs like curriculum materials could institutionalize this approach.

- **Societal Impact:** This methodology could train a new generation of Māori scientists, enhancing STEM participation while grounding innovation in tikanga and whakapapa.

- **Collaboration:** Engage kaupapa Māori leads, DWC scientists, and tohunga to co-design projects.

- **Funding Request:** Seek support for a scalable budget covering venue costs, equipment (LED kits, sensors), catering, and koha, with an indicative total to be finalized.

- **Outcomes:** Develop prototypes (e.g., entangled sensors, mauri-inspired materials), a co-authored whitepaper, and a kaupapa-science working group to sustain collaboration.

QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES

Māori cosmology offers a transformative lens for applying quantum photonics, enriching the Dodd-Walls Centre's research with relational, ethical, and sustainable dimensions. By operationalizing Te Kore, Te Pō, Te Ao Mārama, mauri, mana, and whakapapa, this approach not only advances scientific frontiers but also empowers Māori communities to shape a future where technology reflects their deepest values.

Quantum technology applications represent a frontier where the principles of quantum mechanics—such as superposition, entanglement, and coherence—are harnessed to revolutionize fields like computing, communication, sensing, and imaging. Drawing from the insights in the document *Te Hihiri o Te Ao: Illuminating the Intersections of Mātauranga Māori and Quantum Photonics* and the work of the Dodd-Walls Centre for Photonic and Quantum Technologies (Te Whai Ao), this response outlines key quantum technology applications, emphasizing their potential alignment with Māori cosmological frameworks and practical implementation through the Centre's research capabilities.

1. Quantum Computing

- **Application:** Quantum computers leverage superposition and entanglement to perform complex calculations exponentially faster than classical computers. This is particularly relevant for optimizing problems in cryptography, material simulation, and artificial intelligence.
- **Dodd-Walls Centre Contribution:** The Centre's focus on Quantum Technologies Aotearoa includes advanced computation research. Using ultra-cold atom systems, researchers could develop quantum algorithms tailored to New Zealand's needs, such as optimizing agricultural supply chains or modeling climate systems.
- **Māori Cosmology Alignment:** Te Kore's infinite potential parallels quantum superposition, suggesting a wānanga-based approach to algorithm design that embraces uncertainty as a creative space. This could lead to culturally informed computing paradigms that reflect whakapapa (interconnectedness).
- **Practical Impact:** Enhanced computational power could support Māori-led economic initiatives, such as resource management or indigenous data sovereignty projects.

2. Quantum Communication

- **Application:** Quantum entanglement enables secure communication through protocols like quantum key distribution (QKD), where information is transmitted with cryptographic security impervious to eavesdropping.
- **Dodd-Walls Centre Contribution:** The Centre's expertise in photon entanglement and photonic technologies positions it to pioneer QKD networks. Collaborative projects could establish secure communication links across New Zealand's universities and iwi networks.
- **Māori Cosmology Alignment:** Te Pō's emphasis on relational becoming mirrors entanglement, suggesting ethical frameworks where communication systems respect whanaungatanga (relationships) and kaitiaki responsibilities. Night labs, as proposed in the wānanga, could test these systems.
- **Practical Impact:** This could safeguard sensitive Māori data (e.g., cultural archives) and support secure governance communications, enhancing digital autonomy.

3. Quantum Sensing

- **Application:** Quantum sensors, utilizing superposition and coherence, offer unprecedented precision in detecting gravitational waves, magnetic fields, and environmental changes. Applications include medical diagnostics, geophysical monitoring, and navigation.
- **Dodd-Walls Centre Contribution:** The Centre's work on quantum imaging and sensing aligns with developing ultra-sensitive devices. Research into ultra-cold atoms could lead to sensors for detecting seismic activity or water quality, critical for Aotearoa's earthquake-prone and water-rich landscape.
- **Māori Cosmology Alignment:** Te Ao Mārama's focus on light and visibility, combined with maramataka (lunar cycles), could guide sensor deployment to align with natural rhythms, enhancing sustainability. Mauri's coherence principle could inspire sensors that maintain integrity in dynamic environments.
- **Practical Impact:** Māori communities could use these sensors for kaitiaki roles, monitoring whenua (land) and moana (ocean) health, supporting oranga o te tāiao (environmental well-being).

4. Quantum Imaging

- **Application:** Quantum imaging techniques, such as ghost imaging, use entangled photons to produce high-resolution images with lower light exposure, beneficial for medical, security, and astronomical applications.
- **Dodd-Walls Centre Contribution:** The Centre's photonic research, including next-generation devices, could advance quantum imaging for non-invasive medical diagnostics or environmental mapping. Collaboration with industry partners could commercialize these technologies.
- **Māori Cosmology Alignment:** Te Ao Mārama's transformation of the unseen into the visible resonates with imaging applications, while the cyclical return to Te Kore via karakia ensures ethical use. Whakapapa could inform imaging systems that trace relational histories (e.g., ecological networks).
- **Practical Impact:** This could improve healthcare access for rural Māori communities and support cultural heritage preservation through detailed archaeological imaging.

5. Quantum Materials and Devices

- **Application:** Quantum technologies rely on materials with unique properties, such as superconductors or photonic crystals, for applications in energy storage, quantum communication, and computing hardware.
- **Dodd-Walls Centre Contribution:** Research into ultra-cold atoms and coherence phenomena could lead to the development of novel quantum materials. The Centre's engineering facilities could prototype devices for national infrastructure or agritech.
- **Māori Cosmology Alignment:** Mauri's life force and mana's transformative potential suggest materials with adaptive intelligence, inspired by Atua narratives like Tāwhaki (wave-particle duality). This could guide the design of responsive, sustainable materials.
- **Practical Impact:** Māori-led innovations in renewable energy (e.g., solar panels with quantum efficiency) could enhance iwi economic resilience and align with tikanga-based sustainability.

6. Quantum Simulation

- **Application:** Quantum simulators model complex quantum systems, aiding research in chemistry, physics, and biology—e.g., simulating molecular interactions for drug discovery or climate modeling.

- **Dodd-Walls Centre Contribution:** The Centre’s Beacons program could expand into quantum simulation, using photonic and atomic systems to study ecological or atmospheric processes relevant to Aotearoa.
- **Māori Cosmology Alignment:** The wānanga methodology—cycling through potentiality, incubation, and manifestation—could structure simulations to reflect Te Kore, Te Pō, and Te Ao Mārama, integrating ritual knowledge with scientific inquiry.
- **Practical Impact:** This could support Māori environmental stewardship by modeling the impacts of climate change on whenua, informing adaptive strategies.

CONCLUSION

Quantum technology applications, as advanced by the Dodd-Walls Centre, offer transformative potential across computing, communication, sensing, imaging, materials, and simulation. By integrating Māori cosmological principles—Te Kore, Te Pō, Te Ao Mārama, mauri, mana, and whakapapa—these technologies can be developed with relational ethics and cultural relevance. The proposed wānanga and partnership, may illuminate a path where quantum innovation serves both scientific excellence and the well-being of Aotearoa’s people and environment, reflecting a light beyond the veil.

Appendix B: Brazil — Pathways for Interdisciplinary Engagement between Quantum Science, Arts, and Culture

Local context and structural tensions

Brazil foregrounds a structural tension relevant to global efforts in interdisciplinarity: while recent reforms in secondary education promote integrated curricula and project-based learning, higher education and research remain organised around rigid disciplinary departments, evaluation criteria, and funding streams. This misalignment creates discontinuities across educational stages and makes it difficult for quantum–arts–culture initiatives to be recognised, evaluated, and sustained. At the same time, knowledge—including quantum concepts—is already circulating widely beyond formal institutions, through hybrid, informal, and culturally situated practices.

This annex outlines proposed pathways distilled from a collective dialogue held on 1 December 2025 at Itaú Cultural (São Paulo), titled *Encruzilhada Quântica*, convened by Denise Gadelha, Gabriela Barreto Lemos, and Jane de Almeida, with participation from quantum scientists, artists, educators, philosophers, and cultural agents.

PROPOSED PATHWAYS AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS

1) Creating conditions for shared spaces of co-presence (Short–Medium term)

Interdisciplinary engagement requires environments where disciplinary hierarchies can be temporarily suspended and where shared decision-making and joint recognition are built into collaboration. Participants emphasised the need for conditions that enable co-presence and shared time across disciplines, given the rigidity and separation typical of academic and professional environments.

Three complementary residency approaches can be distinguished: (i) cross-immersion (artists embedded in quantum labs; scientists embedded in cultural production environments); (ii) displaced residencies in settings unfamiliar to all participants (e.g., ecological or rural sites, repurposed spaces), reducing institutional asymmetries; and (iii) community-embedded residencies developed in partnership with local cultural, Indigenous, or territorial initiatives (e.g., community centres or grassroots projects). These partnerships engage directly with place-based knowledge and foster inclusive dialogue beyond conventional academic and artistic circuits. Low-cost pilots can begin quickly; medium-term scaling requires dedicated coordination and support.

2) Low-threshold formats for encounter and exchange (Immediate and ongoing)

Lightweight, recurring formats can extend and sustain shared-space initiatives over time: interdisciplinary lunches and discussion circles; mixed reading groups engaging with quantum science through artistic, philosophical, and cultural perspectives; and informal reciprocal visits between laboratories, cultural spaces, and community contexts.

3) Practices of translation and collective learning (Short–Medium term)

Participants reported experiences with structured practices of translation between quantum science and the arts, including hybrid seminars that combine artistic propositions with hands-on experimentation and open discussion; workshops that require articulating quantum concepts for non-specialist audiences; and collective reflection on how quantum ideas are interpreted, translated, and transformed across practices.

4) Support, recognition, and evaluation (Medium term)

To enable these pathways, alternative support and recognition mechanisms were identified as priorities: pilot funding dedicated to quantum–arts–culture initiatives; mixed evaluation committees (scientists, artists, cultural practitioners); and recognition of exhibitions, performances, open laboratories, and community-based activity as valid outcomes. Partnerships with cultural institutions, foundations, and innovation-oriented organisations—operating in complementarity with academic structures—were highlighted as strategic enablers.

5) Structural targets for long-term alignment (Long term)

Longer-term targets focus on reducing the current disconnect between interdisciplinary intentions in early education and disciplinary rigidity in advanced training and research. Priorities include: interdisciplinary teaching materials and teacher training that include quantum science; assessment models that support integrated learning; flexible academic pathways and career structures; revised evaluation and progression criteria that value interdisciplinary work; and institutional support for programmes operating between quantum science, arts, and culture.

CLOSING NOTE

These pathways reflect locally grounded priorities for enabling inclusive, culturally relevant quantum futures in Brazil. By distinguishing immediate actions from medium- and long-term structural targets, this annex aims to inform UNESCO and partners about practical directions for interdisciplinary engagement between quantum science, arts, and culture, recognising both institutional challenges and the vitality of practices already unfolding beyond formal frameworks.

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